

Addition-Elimination Reactions of Isatins with Arylthiosemicarbazides

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RECENTLY¹ we have reported the reaction of isatins with 2-hydrazinobenzothiazoles which are rather strong nucleophiles. In order to ascertain the behaviour of weak nucleophiles towards isatins a number of arylthiosemicarbazides (which are relatively weak nucleophiles) have now been treated with isatins and the results are reported herein.

Freshly prepared 4-arylthiosemicarbazides (1) were condensed with 4- and 6-chloroisatins in glacial acetic acid. In every instance the reaction underwent smoothly leading to the formation of 3-(4'-arylthiosemicarbazono)-2-indolinones (2). A similar reaction with 4-chloro-1-methylindolin-2,3-dione yielded the expected 2-indolinone (3). With the objective of confirming the structure of 2, these were further treated with morpholine and aqueous formaldehyde resulting in the formation of corresponding morpholinomethyl analogs (4) (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been established on the basis of elemental analyses, ir, pmr and mass spectral data. The pmr spectra of 4a and 4b were in conformity with the assigned structures. It is interesting to note that the deshielding effect of the chloro group in 4a was much more pronounced than in 4b. The mass spectrum of 3 displays a fairly intense molecular ion-peak at m/z 344/346 with a characteristic chlorine isotopic profile.

Experimental

Melting points were taken in open capillaries and are uncorrected. Pmr spectra were taken on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 (90 MHz) instrument with TMS as internal standard and mass spectrum on a Perkin-Elmer Hitachi-RMU-6E (70 eV) instrument.

4-Chloro-1-methyl-indolin-2,3-dione: It was synthesised from 4-chloroisatin according to the reported procedure², (60%), m.p. 193° (lit.³ 191°).

Preparation of 2a: 4-Phenylthiosemicarbazide (1.66 g) was added to a solution of 4-chloroisatin (2.0 g) in methanol (25 ml), followed by a drop of glacial acetic acid. The mixture was refluxed for 2 h, cooled, and the resulting solid, being highly insoluble in common organic solvents, was washed

Scheme 1

with methanol (2 × 25 ml), (70%), m.p. >250°. Other compounds were similarly synthesised: 2b (75%), m.p. >250°; 2c (70%), m.p. 247°, ν_{\max} 3 250 (NH), 1 720 (C=O), 1 600 (C=N) and 1 178 cm⁻¹ (C=S); 2d (72%), m.p. 230–31°.

Preparation of 2e: It was synthesised from 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide and 6-chloroisatin instead of 4-chloroisatin, (79%), m.p. >250°; ν_{\max} 3 220 (NH), 3 190 (NH, ring), 1 698 (C=O), 1 625 (C=N) and 1 155 cm⁻¹ (C=S); δ 6.1–7.0 (9H, m, ArH, NH) and 9.32 (1H, s, =N–NH).

Preparation of 3: A mixture of 4-chloro-1-methyl-indolin-2,3-dione (1.0 g), 4-phenylthiosemicarbazide (0.84 g) and ethanol (10 ml) containing a drop of glacial acetic acid as catalyst was refluxed on a water-bath for 2 h. The resulting solid that separated on cooling was recrystallised from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 234°, m/z 344/346 (M^+).

Preparation of 4a: Morpholine (0.5 ml) and formalin (0.5 ml) were added to a hot solution of 4-chloro-2-(4'-phenylthiosemicarbazono)-2-indolinone (1.65 g) in DMF (5 ml) containing methanol (10 ml). The mixture was heated on a water-bath with occasional shaking. The resulting solid was washed with cold methanol (2 × 2 ml) and recrystallised from chloroform to yield a pure product as indicated by tlc, (65%), m.p. 207–08°; δ 2.75 (4H, t, J 4.2 Hz, N(CH₂)₂), 3.88 (4H, t, J , 4.2 Hz, O(CH₂)₂), 4.66

(2H, s, N-CH₂-N), 7.2-8.15 (9H, m, ArH, NH) and 9.98 τ (1H, s, =N-NH).

4b was prepared similarly using 6-chloroisatin and was recrystallised from chloroform, (63%), m.p. 175°; δ 2.52 (4H, t, J 4.2 Hz, N(CH₂)₂), 3.61 (4H, t, J 4.2 Hz, O(CH₂)₂), 4.36 (2H, s, N-CH₂N), 6.9-7.7 (9H, m, ArH, NH) and 9.35 (1H, s, =N-NH).

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